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CORPORATE GOVERNANCE, MANAGERIAL OWNERSHIP AND CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC BANKS

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A good corporate governance and managerial ownership can strengthen financial stability and reduce bank risk. We investigate how corporate governance and managerial ownership affect credit risk in listed Islamic banks working in Asian countries by taking sample size from 2011 to 2023. We employ fixed effect technique for analyzing the study data. We find that board structure such as board size, board independence, and board meetings have significant and negative effects on credit risk. However, high managerial proportion of ownership has incentive to decrease credit risk of banks.

Keywords: Board independence, board size, board meetings, corporate governance, managerial ownership, credit risk, Islamic banks

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1. Introduction

Instead of the normal banking system, Islamic banking and finance emerged to offer ways to investment in businesses, trade, and borrow money mainly in accordance with Shari'ah. Islamic banking and finance have attracted significant interest in recent years because of their rapid development and a series of financial crises in the past decade, with the global financial crisis of 2007-2009 being the most severe (Ibrahim, 2015). Islamic banking supports ethical and asset-backed investments with focus primarily on sharing of risk (Jatmiko *et al.*, 2024). According to Sallemi *et al.* (2023), the banking sector's main objective is to ensure the smooth working and stability of their economic and financial progress. Risk taking behavior of financial institutions has become a major research issue after 2008 financial crisis (Moussa, 2019).

The advancements of the Islamic banks have motivated scholars to investigate empirical research on risk related activities Islamic banks as compared to conventional banks (Kabir *et al.*, 2015). Liquidity risk exists in both conventional and Islamic banking systems (Ghenimi *et al.*, 2021). It is challenging for banks to respond promptly when a payment is required due to liquidity risk. Managing liquidity risk enables banks to fulfill their financial responsibilities, which may be affected by external factors and bank governance. Banks may face solvency issues if liquidity risk is not properly addressed and managed (Asongu, 2013). Furthermore, this risk compels the bank to immediately dispose of its valuable financial asset at a lower price than its market value (Arif & Anees, 2012). Banks have historically employed financial products that are interest-based. However, Islamic institutions are unable to use these interest related activities. As a result, they face challenges to manage credit risk, which is one of the major concerns of Islamic banks. Furthermore, due the Shariah principles which Islamic banks follow, some of the Shariah based financial products incur extra credit risk on banking operations (Kabir *et al.*, 2015). Credit risk means the non-payment of a loan by borrower in accordance as per requirements of the contract (Safiullah & Shamsuddin, 2018). Islamic banks are exposed to more credit risk in profit and loss sharing modes because of moral hazard among borrowers who show interest to share loss with banks (El-Hawary *et al.*, 2007). According to Orazalin and Mahmood (2019), better corporate governance practices promoted to more effective bank operating outcomes after the period of

financial crisis because inefficient corporate governance is regarded as an important factor that leads to crisis (Nguyen, 2022).

Islamic banks have Shariah supervisory board which have influence on credit risk (Umar *et al.*, 2023b) and face more credit risk as opposed to conventional banks because of more complexity in generating finance (Mokni *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, it is important to manage the activities that lead to credit risk. Strong corporate governance structure is essential in Islamic banking to deal with such risk. Corporate governance is comprised of a set of regulations and organizational frameworks Naciti *et al.* (2021). Many countries depend on applying corporate governance practices to boost economic dynamism or enhance overall economic performance (Haw *et al.*, (2010). Ownership structure is component or mechanism and the most important aspects of corporate governance. Because it establishes the power dynamics inside a firm and has a direct impact on corporate governance procedures and behavior. According to Hunjra *et al.* (2020), the ownership structure has a significant impact on financing decisions, firm value, and even insolvency risk reduction. An effective ownership structure is an internal corporate governance framework that can help resolve disputes between the owners and managers of the company (Haque *et al.*, 2011). Managerial ownership may lead to align the interests of both the shareholders and the managers. As per the concept of agency theory of Jensen and Meckling (1976), the managers are supposed to be risk averse and more careful when they have greater interest in the bank because their financial stake is connected to the outcomes of banks.

This suggests that corporate governance practices are designed to align the interests of shareholders with those of management. Ownership structure is a crucial component of corporate governance procedures since managers with greater authority typically distribute profits to shareholders (Jo & Pan, 2009). Banks' risk-taking behavior has evolved as a result of reforms occurring in ownership structure (Barry *et al.*, 2011). Empirical research on corporate governance has mostly focused on the ownership structure's function in monitoring management and its connection to risk-taking, since it is a crucial aspect of internal bank governance (Macey and O'hara., 2003). The academic and regulatory communities have shown significant concern in the past few years regarding the need to address risk-taking behavior in banks (Otero *et al.*, 2019). This is crucial because excessive risk-taking not only puts individual banks at risk but also has the

potential to destabilize the entire financial sector if risks spread to other institutions through contagion (DeYoung & Torna, 2013).

For a long time, ownership structure of banking firms remained a center of interest for economists. Another area of importance with respect to managerial ownership along with corporate governance and their effect on credit risk of Islamic banks still needs attention. Ownership structure may be particularly crucial to corporate governance in the banking sector. This is due to the fact that regulations frequently oblige banks to maintaining a specific level of capital, which can be altered by bank ownership. According to Nguyen *et al.* (2015) that highly concentrated ownership overcomes weak governance by monitoring the actions of managers which reduces the chances of default. The banking industry serves an important part in the financial systems of Asian nations because an effective banking system is necessary for the development of their economies (Nisar *et al.*, 2018). Corporate governance of banks in developing countries is not progressed as compared to developed countries (Nawaz, 2019). Therefore, banks in developing countries need strong governance structure to deal with risk related activities.

Taking the sample from 2011 to 2023, the primary objective of the current study is to examine the effect of corporate governance and managerial ownership on credit risk of Islamic banks operating in Asian countries which include Pakistan, Indonesia, Malaysia, and Bangladesh. Our study is different from previous studies and make significant contribution. Understanding these connections helps researchers create a more comprehensive understanding of how to enhance corporate governance to lower bank risk while considering ownership structure.

The structure of this paper is organized as follows: after this introduction, Section 2 presents the literature review and hypotheses. Section 3 presents the data source and describes the methodologies used in the paper. Section 4 presents the analysis and results. Section 5 presents the discussion and conclusions.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Formulation

Islamic banks must control credit risk in order to maintain stability and enhance performance. According to the views of Ferhi (2018), credit risk is one of the main causes of instability in banking system. Kakar *et al.* (2021) determine that the external corporate governance processes of regulator and regulation are associated with controlling the bank and enhancing the risk

management process and study hypothesizes that better corporate governance will lead to better risk management. There are several observed and unobserved bank traits, which make corporate governance and bank risk taking substantially connected. The way the board operates, the ownership structure, and external control are examples of these bank features. The following section presents brief review of literature arguing the focus of present study.

2.1. Board size and credit risk

It is broadly recognized that the board size is an internal mechanism or component of corporate governance and play an important role in firm's management (Adams *et al.*, 2010). Moreover, Llewellyn and Sinha (2000) determine that the foundation of internal corporate governance is the board of directors, which is the bank's highest governing body and is in charge of determining the institution's strategic direction as well as supervising its risk management practices. Thus, the board plays an important role in the internal governance with monitoring and controlling function. Sierra *et al.* (2006) suggest that strong board improves bank performance. There is some studies relating to board of director size and banking risk with some conflicting results. Pathan and Fuff (2013) find in their studies of European banks that bank with less board size are more efficient. However, Brick and Chidambaran (2008) provide the evidences that there is negative relationship between board size and risk-taking behavior of banks. Similarly, Grassa and Matoussi (2014), in the framework of agency theory support that large board size has the potential to monitor the decisions of top management, risks and to reduce the agency costs. Accordingly, our hypothesis is constructed as follow;

H1: There is negative effect of bank size on credit risk.

2.2. Board Independence and credit risk

The outside independent directors, contribute positively to effective control of managers in consideration to exercise control (Fama & Jensen, 1983). Lin *et al.* (2009) report that the independence of board of directors is closely related to an increase the efficiency of firms and leads to good practice of corporate governance. Lau *et al.* (2009) examine that an independent board member may exercise effective control over managers, and it promotes corporate performance. The previous studies results explain that board independence matters for controlling risk. Pathan (2009) examines a negative association between the proportion of non-executive directors on the board and the level of risk-taking by banks. Adams and Mehran (2012) find that

greater independence might be inefficient in more complex institutions such as banks and other financial institutions. Maier and Yurtoglu (2022) also reports a negative relationship between independent directors and risk taking of banks.

Raheja (2005) examine that the independent directors often lead to inferior decisions due to their limited knowledge and understanding of the firm. In addition, Further, Khan *et al.* (2017) documents that non-executive directors add value to the firm by enhancing performance because of having better skills expertise, skills, and extensive experience, hence they can manage and control risk. When an independent director on board increase the firm is less likely to face financial fraud and financial risk is reduced (Beasley, 1996). The study explain that independent board will not want to encourage excessive risk-taking with the fear that when the bank fails their reputation will be on the line and as such are likely to be associated with lower risk-taking behavior. In line with the above argument, the study hypothesizes that:

H2: There is negative effect of board independence on credit risk.

2.3. Board meetings and credit risk

Counting the number of board members present at meetings is one of the simplest ways to assess the performance of the board Chou and Buchdadi (2017). They perform their responsibility of monitoring and advising the firm more intensely with regular meetings. In addition, from the previous research, Chou *et al.* (2013) indicate that board meetings improve the success of the firm and make positive impact on firm performance. It is noted, therefore, that the board members should attend the meeting individually rather than through a representative. Nguyen (2022) identifies that more frequency in board meetings is useful for stable banking operations and improves monitoring role. Further, board meetings may be considered as important way while gathering information related to firm as noted by Adams and Ferreira (2007). This means that that more timely and regular meetings may have quick response of the board of directors to market change which minimizes risk. Regular meetings show a reasonable awareness regarding their operational decisions to enhance financial outcome. Adu (2023) concludes that the number of board meetings has a negative impact on bank risk-taking. From the above discussion, the study develops the following hypothesis.

H3: There is negative effect of board meetings on credit risk.

2.4. Managerial ownership and bank risk-taking

Corporate governance may have different effects on bank risk taking depending on the ownership structure of banks (Laeven & Levine, 2009). However, the presence of managerial ownership, the influence of board of directors in major decision making including risk taking activities is affected. In order to protect their interests, banks have a number of controls on management. The ownership structure acknowledges a critical role in enhancing the quality of the information revealed and the risk management process. Managers are predicted to be less risk-takers under the agency theory because they could be more concerned with maintaining their reputation and job security (Angkinand & Wihlborg, 2010). Considering this, Ehsan and Javid (2018) emphasize that managerial ownership has negative impact on bank risk-taking and ownership structure is one of the major factors of risk-taking. Kakar *et al.* (2021) find that relationship between ownership structure, corporate governance and risk management is more sensitive for bank performance. The bank's owners play a vital role in promoting the institution and maintaining good corporate governance practices. To coordinate the owner's interests, the owner's approach is to determine and exert control over the manager.

Managerial ownership gives managers the ability to control the firm operations and determine what policies and plans it follows because in this case the managers also act as a shareholders. Managerial ownership is an effective corporate governance mechanism for reducing the agency problem. Bouwens and Verriest (2014) argue that managers holding equity of their bank take less risk because they have fewer opportunities to diversify risk compared with outside shareholders. Otero *et al.* (2019) claim that compared to management, shareholders are more willing to take on risk because they can diversify their money and because they stand to earn more from increased risk-taking. According to Bouwens and Verriest (2014), banks under shareholder control often take greater risk than banks under managerial ownership. We propose the following hypothesis.

H4: There is negative effect of managerial ownership on credit risk.

3. Methodology

We base our analysis on panel data of 53 listed Islamic banks operating in Asia such as Pakistan, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Bangladesh. These Islamic banks provide both debt and equity based Islamic products such as Ijara, Murabaha, Musharakah, and Mudarabah. We gather data from DataStream covering broad range of the time period between 2011 and 2023. We used non-performing loans (NPL) and Z-score to measure credit risk of banks because of their conventional relevance and strength in determining the stability and financial health of banks. Further, NPL is the direct measure of bank credit risk. We employ fixed effect model as the primary statistical technique for analysis purpose. This regression technique enables controlling for time-invariant unobservable individual effects. When unobserved effects are correlated with explanatory variables of the study, employing fixed effect is suitable. However, in case where explanatory variables are proved to be random, a random effect model is preferred. Further, in ordinary least square (OLS), such unobserved factors that are unique to each bank of the sample are not considered which might give misleading and biased outcomes. Fixed effect model is more suitable for panel data estimation where we analyze the change within bank and ignoring bank specific features. Therefore, considering these factors and unobserved characteristics relevant to banks, we use fixed effect model. However, description and measurement relating to variables of the study are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of variables

Variables	Abbr.	Measurements	Reference/s
Non-performing loan	NPL	Percentage of loan loss to total amount of loan	Adem (2023)
Z-score	ZSR	Sum of ROA and ETA over standard deviation of ROA	Hunjra <i>et al.</i> (2024)
Managerial Ownership	MNO	Ratio of shares held by management	Bouwens and Verriest (2014)
Board Independence	BI	Independent directors on the board measured as percentage	Sarkar and Sarkar (2018)
Board Size	BS	Total number of board members	Uddin <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Board Meetings	BMT	Number of board meetings in a year	Hunjra <i>et al.</i> (2024)
Assets Growth	GRT	Annual percentage change in total assets	Hunjra <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Bank Size	SZ	Natural log of a bank's total assets	Hunjra <i>et al.</i> (2024)
Return on Assets	ROA	Net income over assets	Kayakus <i>et al.</i> (2023)

3.2. Model specification

We apply the following statistical model for examining the data.

$$(CRR)_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1(BSZ)_{i,t} + \beta_2(BIND)_{i,t} + \beta_3(BMTG)_{i,t} + \beta_4(MON)_{i,t} + \beta_5(GRT)_{i,t} + \beta_6(SZ)_{i,t} + \beta_7(ROA)_{i,t} + \mu_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where, β represents beta, α is alpha, and μ shows error term.

4. Results

We provide descriptive statistics in Table 2 showing the summary of data. However, there are not much deviations in the values which reveals that data does not have outliers, and therefore follows the same trend. Further, the outcomes of descriptive statistics show that values of each variable have normal distribution. In addition, Table 3 displays correlation analysis for the explanatory variables of the study for confirming the strength of relationships. Findings justify that there is no strong correlation among variables confirming absence of multicollinearity problems in the data.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis

Variables	Mean	S.D	NPL	ZSR	MNO	BI	BS	BMT	GRT	SZ	ROA
NPL	0.104	0.353	1								
ZSR	3.492	0.496	-0.059	1							
MNO	0.217	0.536	-0.142	0.215	1						
BI	0.197	0.281	-0.086	0.103	0.067	1					
BS	7.836	0.552	-0.138	0.273	-0.151	0.058	1				
BMT	4.037	0.738	-0.182	0.084	0.075	0.072	0.121	1			
GRT	0.015	0.619	-0.074	0.134	0.124	-0.256	0.056	0.274	1		
SZ	17.163	0.881	-0.091	0.122	-0.116	-0.302	0.092	0.161	0.124	1	
ROA	0.171	0.934	0.105	-0.057	0.089	0.178	-0.219	0.059	-0.057	0.196	1

In addition, in Table 3, we also employ VIF test to check for potential multicollinearity issue which may appear due to overlapping of relevant variables. The outcomes are within the range of 10 (Nguyen *et al.*, 2014) which shows multicollinearity problem does not appear in the model.

Table 3. Test for multicollinearity

	VIF	1/VIF
BMT	1.327	0.754
BI	1.515	0.660
GRT	1.344	0.744
MNO	1.425	0.702
ROA	1.694	0.590
BS	1.296	0.772
SZ	1.542	0.649

Table 4. Fixed effect estimation

	Dependent variable: NPL		Dependent variable: ZSR	
	Coeff.	T-values	Coeff.	T-values
BS	-0.075***	(-8.236)	0.141**	(2.319)
BI	-0.006***	(-10.208)	0.075**	(2.286)
BMT	-0.122***	(-5.631)	0.047***	(7.635)
MON	-0.002***	(-6.162)	0.042***	(5.063)
GRT	0.424**	(2.196)	-0.605*	(-1.795)
ROA	-0.251*	(-1.825)	0.163**	(2.421)
SZ	0.467*	(1.837)	-0.245*	(-1.786)
Country FE	Yes		Yes	
Covid-19	Yes		Yes	
C	0.042***	(6.517)	-0.211***	(-4.635)
F-Stat	12.562***		10.635***	
R-square	0.412		0.378	
P-values of Likelihood test	0.000		0.001	
P-values of Hausman test	0.000		0.000	

Regression results concerning to fixed effect model are provided in Table 4. We find that large board size has significantly reduced credit risk in banks which supports the arguments of agency theory that large board size has the potential to monitor the decisions of top management, risk related activities, and to reduce the agency costs (Grassa & Matoussi, 2014). For further smooth operations and better controlling credit risk, board of directors encourages risk management committee to reduce the risk related operations within banks (Umar *et al.*, 2023c). In addition, board of directors also appoints such members of audit committee who can assist prevent Islamic banks while taking more credit risk (Umar *et al.*, 2023a). Similarly, with more monitoring

abilities, independent directors have potential to control credit risk in the banks. Maier and Yurtoglu (2022) conclude the same outcomes in their study indicating a negative impact of large board on bank credit risk as also indicated by Umar *et al.* (2024). Results further show that more frequency in board meetings is beneficial for banks to get positive outcomes while taking fruitful financial decisions. Therefore, more board meetings provide chance to board of directors to discuss the matters of banks to avoid from harmful risky decision. In addition, with more board meetings, banks can make better risk management practices, strategic plans, and improve financial health of the banks with sharing experience and knowledge. The negative impact of board meetings on credit risk is similar to the study investigated by Adu (2023). With increase in managerial ownership, bank credit risk is significantly reduced because when management holds more shares, they are more effective and risk management process is also improved. When managers own more shares, they are more likely to be conscious about the interest of the firms and shareholders instead of their own interest. Furthermore, managerial ownership is careful about risky loan decisions as when creditors are unable to pay back loans, managerial ownership is also adversely affected which might lead them to financial stability. Therefore, with having shares of the banks, managerial ownership takes less risky decisions and has significantly decreased credit risk in Islamic banks as supported by Ehsan and Javid (2018). Board independence has significant and negative influence on credit risk of banks suggesting that banks with independent directors have better risk management policies due to monitoring power of independent directors. They do not allow management to make such policies which may result in increasing credit risk and bank failure. Relating to the control variables of the study, they reveal mixed findings depending on the varying business settings of the selected countries.

5. Conclusion

The main objective of our study is to evaluate the potential effects of board structure and ownership structure on credit risk of Islamic banks operating in South countries. We employ fixed effect regression estimate. Findings of our study reveal that corporate governance and ownership structure play a significant role in affecting credit risk of banks. We find that board size, board independence, board meetings, and managerial ownership have significant and negative impact on credit risk of Islamic banks. Our findings provide policy implications for managers, investors, and policymakers. These policy implications aim to enhance the general stability and risk

administration of Islamic banks through better governance, more managerial ownership and aligning the interests.

Islamic banks should maintain the optimum level of board of directors to better control for credit risk. More independent directors may enhance risk management practices which ultimately reduces credit risk. Further, independent directors have more expertise and knowledge with unbiased opinion along with monitoring power over the operations of management. Therefore, it is imperative to keep a suitable number of outside directors to manage credit risk within the framework of Islamic banks. More incentive to managers in the form of more shares may be useful to align the interests of management and the owners. Therefore, management should be motivated to buy higher portion of shares in order to stabilize the banking operations. Our study can be broadened by considering moderating factors such as audit quality and social factors. Further, the same study may consider more corporate governance elements including more measures of ownership structure. Sample set can be increased by considering more Islamic countries for better analysis in future research. Future study may take the role of Shariah board in corporate governance and managing credit risk within Islamic banks. Lastly, managerial ownership traits such as educational background, experience, and tenure represent factors that influence internal control and decision making. Therefore, in future research, these factors may also be considered in the same study.

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